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PDSLS: An approximation SINR-based Shortest Link Scheduling algorithm with power control

Abstract: In this paper, we examine the Shortest Link Scheduling (SLS) issue in wireless networks within the context of the Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise-Ratio (SINR) interference model with oblivious power control, and propose an approximation Diamond-based SLS with Power control (PDSLS) algorithm. Given that numerous nodes within wireless networks operate on battery power, minimizing the transmission power not only reduces interference but also conserves energy. We adopt a novel link classification approach, reducing nodes' transmission power without generating "black and gray" links. We schedule links belonging to each class by dividing the link deployment plane into diamonds. The validity and efficacy of our algorithm are demonstrated through theoretical analysis and simulation outcomes. Numerical analysis shows that our approximation ratio is tighter than the best known ones in state-of-the-art algorithms. Simulation results demonstrate that the proposed algorithm effectively reduces the transmission power and the number of required time slots compared to the state-of-the-art algorithms.

Keywords: Shortest Link Scheduling, SINR, Power control, Wireless communications

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